

Properties on Topologized Domination in Neutrosophic Graphs

R.Narmada Devi¹ and G.Muthumari²

Department of Mathematics, Vel Tech Rangarajan Dr. Sagunthala R & D Institute of Science and Technology, Chennai, India.

¹narmadadevi23@gmail.com, ¹drnarmadadevi@veltech.edu.in, and ²mathsgmm@gmail.com

Abstract: In this paper, the new concept Topologized domination on Neutrosophic Graphs is introduced. The idea of N-Top domination is discussed in cycle, path, complete graph, star graph. The basic properties of N-Top dom set, N-Top minimum dom set, N-Top minimal dom set are introduced and N-Top dom number is also established with some necessary examples.

Keywords: N-Top dom set, N-Top minimum dom set, N-Top minimal dom set, N-Top dom number.

1 Introduction

The concept of topologized graph was introduced by Antoine Vella in 2005 [1]. Antoine Vella extended topology to the topologized graph by the S_1 space and the boundary of every vertex and edges of a graph G . The space is called S_1 space if every singleton in the topological space either open or closed. Chang [5] introduced the concept of the notion of fuzzy topology. In 2017, topologized graph extended to Topologized bipartite graph Topologized Hamiltonian and complete graph by vimala.s et al [13,14]. Ore [9] introduced the concept of theory of domination of graph. In 1997 T.Heynes, S. Hedetniemi and P. Slater published the book, "Fundamentals of domination in graphs" [6]. After this publication there has been a rapid growth of research on this area and a wide variety of domination parameters have been introduced.

Bhuvaneswari et. al [4] handled the concept of topologized domination in graph and explained some of its properties. Smarandache [10] was first person introduced the idea of neutrosophic theory. He discussed some types of neutrosophic sets like Over, Under/Off sets etc., [12]. He extended work on HyperGraph to n-SuperHyperGraph and to Plithogenic n-SuperHyperGraph, and Extension of HyperAlgebra to n-ary (Classical-/Neutro-/Anti-) HyperAlgebra [11]. Smarandache has introduced in 2020 the n-SuperHyperGraph, with super-vertices [that are groups of vertices] and hyper-edges defined on power-set of power-set... that is the most general form of graph as today, and n-HyperAlgebra. A SuperHyperGraph, is a HyperGraph (where a group of Edges form a HyperEdge) such that a group of vertices are united all together into a SuperVertex like a group of people (=vertices) that are united all together into an organization (=SuperVertex); and further on the n-SuperHyperGraph where many groups (=SuperVertices) are united all together to form a group-of-groups (called 2-SuperVertex, or Type-2 SuperVertex), then a group of Type-2 SuperVertices forms a Type-3 SuperVertex, ..., and so on up to Type-n SuperVertex, for any $n \geq 1$, which better reflects our reality. Later Narmada Devi [7,8] worked on new type of neutrosophic off graph and minimal domination via neutrosophic over graph. In this article, the novel of topologized domination of N-graphs are developed and some of its interesting properties are established.

2 Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [4] A topologized graph is a topological space \mathcal{H} such that

- (i) every singleton is open or closed
- (ii) $\forall h \in \mathcal{H}, |\partial(h)| \leq 2$, since $\partial(h)$ is denoted by the boundary of a point h .

Definition 2.2. [8] A set \mathcal{S} of vertices of \mathcal{G} is said to be a top domination set \mathcal{S} if \mathcal{G} is a top graph and every vertex in $\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{G}) - \mathcal{S}$ is adjacent to atleast one vertex of in \mathcal{S} .

Definition 2.3. [8] The minimum cardinality among all the top dom set of \mathcal{G} is called the top dom number of G and it is denoted by $\tau\gamma(\mathcal{G})$.

Definition 2.4. [8] A Ngraph is a pair $\mathcal{G} = (P, Q)$ of a crisp graph $\mathcal{G}^* = (V, E)$ where P is N vertex set in V and Q is a N edge set in E such that

- (i) $\mathcal{I}_Q(m_i m_j) \leq \mathcal{I}_P(m_i) \wedge \mathcal{I}_P(m_j)$
- (ii) $\mathcal{I}_Q(m_i m_j) \leq \mathcal{I}_P(m_i) \wedge \mathcal{I}_P(m_j)$
- (iii) $\mathcal{F}_Q(m_i m_j) \geq \mathcal{F}_P(m_i) \vee \mathcal{F}_P(m_j) (m_i, m_j) \in E$

3 Neutrosophic Topologized Domination Graphs

An important concept of N-Top dom in graphs with suitable examples are discussion this section. Throughout this paper $\mathcal{G}^* = (V, E)$ denotes a crisp graph and $\mathcal{G} = (P, Q)$ a Ngraph.

Definition 3.1. A Ngraph \mathcal{G} is called N-Top graph if \mathcal{G}^* satisfy the following condition

- (i) every singleton is open or closed
- (ii) $\forall h \in \mathcal{H}, |\partial(h)| \leq 2$, since $\partial(h)$ is denoted by the boundary of a point h .

Definition 3.2. A set \mathcal{S} of vertices of \mathcal{G} is said to be N-Top dom set in \mathcal{G} if \mathcal{G} is a N-Top graph and every vertex in $\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{G}) - \mathcal{S}$ is adjacent to atleast one vertex in \mathcal{S} at the degree of truth, indeterminacy and falsity-membership belongs to $[0, 1]$ such that $0 \leq \mathcal{I}_P(m) + \mathcal{I}_P(m) + \mathcal{F}_P(m) \leq 3, \forall m \in V$

Example 3.1.

Figure 1: S_3 -star graph

Let $\mathcal{H} = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, (0.5, 0.2, 0.6), (0.4, 0.1, 1)\}$ be a topological space defined by the topology $\tau = \{\mathcal{H}, \emptyset, \{a_1\}, \{a_2\}, \{a_3\}, \{a_1, a_2\}, \{a_1, a_3\}, \{a_2, a_3\}\}$. Here for every $\{h\} \in \mathcal{H}$ is open or closed and $|\partial(h)| \leq 2$. By the definition of 3.1, $\mathcal{G} = (P, Q)$ is N-Top graph. Also N-top dom sets by $\mathcal{D}_1 = \{a_2\}$ and $\mathcal{D}_2 = \{a_1, a_3\}$.

Theorem 3.1. Let \mathcal{G} be a N-Top graph with atmost degree two. If \mathcal{S} is a top dom set of \mathcal{G} , then it is a N-Top dom set of \mathcal{G} .

Proof:

Let \mathcal{H} be a topological space with topology τ defined by $V \cup E$. Since every singleton set is open or closed and \mathcal{G} is a N-graph where the truth, indeterminacy and falsity membership function with unit interval $[0, 1]$ such that $0 \leq \mathcal{T}_P(m) + \mathcal{I}_P(m) + \mathcal{F}_P(m) \leq 3, \forall m \in V$ and atmost degree two. Hence $|\partial(h)| \leq 2$. This implies that \mathcal{G} is N-Top graph. Let \mathcal{S} be top dom set then every vertex in $\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{G}) - \mathcal{S}$ is adjacent to atleast one vertex of \mathcal{S} thus implies that \mathcal{S} is a N-Top dom set of \mathcal{G} .

Example 3.2.

Let a_1, a_2, a_3 and a_4 denote the vertices and $(0.1, 0.4, 0.8), (0.2, 0.4, 0.9), (0.1, 0.4, 0.2), (0.3, 0.5, 0.4)$ denote the edges which are labelled $f(0.1, 0.4, 0.8) = \{a_1, a_2\}, f(0.2, 0.4, 0.9) = \{a_2, a_3\}, f(0.1, 0.4, 0.2) = \{a_3, a_4\}, f(0.3, 0.5, 0.4) = \{a_4, a_1\}$,

Let a_1, a_2, a_3 and a_4 denote the vertices and $(0.1, 0.4, 0.8), (0.2, 0.4, 0.9), (0.1, 0.4, 0.2), (0.3, 0.5, 0.4)$ denote the edges.

Let $\mathcal{H} = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, (0.1, 0.4, 0.2), (0.3, 0.5, 0.4), (0.1, 0.4, 0.8), (0.2, 0.4, 0.9)\}$ be a topological space defined by the topology

$$\tau = \left\{ \mathcal{H}, \emptyset, \{a_1\}, \{a_2\}, \{a_3\}, \{a_4\}, \{a_1, a_2\}, \{a_1, a_3\}, \{a_1, a_4\}, \{a_2, a_3\}, \{a_2, a_4\}, \{a_3, a_4\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_4\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_4\}, \{a_1, a_3, a_4\} \right\}$$

Here for every $\{h\} \in \mathcal{H}$ is open and $|\partial(h)| \leq 2$. We have $\partial(a_1) = \{a_2, a_4\}, \partial(a_2) = \{a_1, a_3\}, \partial(a_3) = \{a_2, a_4\}$ and $\partial(a_4) = \{a_1, a_3\}$ with $|\partial(h_i)| = 2$ where $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

Hence this graph is a N-Top graph.

Then $D = \{a_1, a_3\}$ and $\{a_2, a_4\}$ is a N-Top dom set in V whose maximum and minimum degrees of $\mathcal{T}, \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{F}$ respectively.

	\mathcal{T}_A	\mathcal{I}_A	\mathcal{F}_A
a_1	0.4	0.7	0.3
a_2	0.2	0.5	0.8
a_3	0.3	0.9	0.1
a_4	0.6	0.5	0.2

	a_1a_2	a_2a_3	a_3a_4	a_4a_1
$\mathcal{T}_{m_i \cup m_j} = \max \langle m_i, m_j \rangle$	0.4	0.3	0.6	0.6
$\mathcal{I}_{m_i \cup m_j} = \max \langle m_i, m_j \rangle$	0.7	0.9	0.9	0.7
$\mathcal{F}_{m_i \cap m_j} = \min \langle m_i, m_j \rangle$	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.2

	a_1a_2	a_2a_3	a_3a_4	a_4a_1
$\mathcal{I}_{m_i \cap m_j} = \min \langle m_i, m_j \rangle$	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.4
$\mathcal{S}_{m_i \cap m_j} = \min \langle m_i, m_j \rangle$	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
$\mathcal{F}_{m_i \cup m_j} = \max \langle m_i, m_j \rangle$	0.8	0.8	0.2	0.3

Therefore this graph is N-TOP dom graph.

Definition 3.3. A dominating set \mathcal{S} of the N-Top graph \mathcal{G} is said to be a minimal N-Top dom set if for every vertex v in \mathcal{S} , $\mathcal{S} - \{v\}$ is not a of \mathcal{S} is a N-Top dom set. i.e., no proper subset of \mathcal{S} is a N-Top dom set.

Example 3.3. From Example 1, $\{a_1, a_3\}$ is N-Top minimal dom set but which is not a N-Top dom set.

Theorem 3.2. Let \mathcal{G} be a N-Top graph with atmost degree two. If \mathcal{S} is a N-TOP minimum dom set, then D is a N-Top minimal dom set.

Proof:

Let \mathcal{H} be a topological space with topology τ defined by $V \cup E$.

Since every singleton set is open or closed and \mathcal{G} is a N-graph where the truth, indeterminacy and falsity membership function with unit interval $[0, 1]$ such that $0 \leq \mathcal{I}_P(m) + \mathcal{S}_P(m) + \mathcal{F}_P(m) \leq 3, \forall m \in V$ and atmost degree two. Hence $|\partial(h)| \leq 2$. This implies that \mathcal{G} is N-Top graph.

Let \mathcal{S} be a top minimum dom set. Then every $v \in \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{S} - \{v\}$ is not a top dom set which implies that \mathcal{S} is a N-Top minimal dom set.

Remark 3.1. The converse of the above theorem need not by true. Since every graph need not be a N-Top graph. Consider the following example.

Example 3.4. Let \mathcal{G} be a N complete graph K_4 with 4 vertices.

Figure 2: K_4 N-complete graph

Here every singleton sets are minimum dominating sets. Clearly the complete graph K_4 is not a N-Top graph, since $n \geq 4$. Then the a N-Top dom set does exists. Then the dom sets need not be a N-Top dom set.

Lemma .1. Let P_n be a N-path with n vertices which is a N-Top graph. Then the N-Top dom number is $\tau_\gamma(P_n) \geq \lceil n/3 \rceil$.

Example 3.5.

Let a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4 and a_5 denote the vertices and $(0.2, 0.4, 0.7), (0.1, 0.3, 0.6), (0.2, 0.5, 0.9), (0.3, 0.1, 0.9)$ denote the edges which are labelled $f(0.2, 0.4, 0.7) = \{a_1, a_2\}, f(0.1, 0.3, 0.6) = \{a_2, a_3\}, f(0.2, 0.5, 0.9) = \{a_3, a_4\}, f(0.3, 0.1, 0.9) = \{a_4, a_5\}$,

Let $\mathcal{H} = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, (0.2, 0.4, 0.7), (0.1, 0.3, 0.6), (0.2, 0.5, 0.9), (0.3, 0.1, 0.9)\}$ be a topological space defined by the topology

$$\tau = \left\{ \mathcal{H}, \emptyset, \{a_1\}, \{a_2\}, \{a_3\}, \{a_4\}, \{a_5\}, \{a_1, a_2\}, \{a_1, a_3\}, \{a_1, a_4\}, \{a_1, a_5\}, \{a_2, a_3\}, \{a_2, a_4\}, \{a_2, a_5\}, \{a_3, a_4\}, \{a_3, a_5\}, \{a_4, a_5\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_4\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_5\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_4\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_5\}, \{a_3, a_4, a_5\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_5\} \right\}$$

Here for every $\{h\} \in \mathcal{H}$ is open and $|\partial(h)| \leq 2$. By the definition 3.1, it is a N-Top graph.

Then $\mathcal{S} = \{a_2, a_5\}$ is a N-Top dom set in V whose maximum and minimum degrees of $\mathcal{T}, \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{F}$ respectively.

	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5
\mathcal{T}_A	0.7	0.3	0.2	0.4	0.5
\mathcal{I}_A	0.4	0.5	0.8	0.7	0.1
\mathcal{F}_A	0.6	0.1	0.5	0.8	0.9

	a_1a_2	a_2a_3	a_3a_4	a_4a_5
$\mathcal{T}_B(\min)$	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.3
$\mathcal{I}_B(\min)$	0.4	0.3	0.5	0.1
$\mathcal{F}_B(\max)$	0.7	0.6	0.9	0.9

	a_1a_2	a_2a_3	a_3a_4	a_4a_5
$\mathcal{T}_B(\max)$	0.7	0.3	0.4	0.5
$\mathcal{I}_B(\max)$	0.5	0.8	0.8	0.7
$\mathcal{F}_B(\min)$	0.6	0.5	0.8	0.9

The N-Top dom set is $\mathcal{S} = \{a_2, a_5\}$.

$$\tau_\gamma(P_5) = \lceil 5/3 \rceil = \lceil 1.666 \rceil = 2.$$

Therefore this graph is N-Top dom graph.

Example 3.6.

Let $a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6$ and a_7 denote the vertices and $(0.3, 0.2, 0.6), (0.2, 0.1, 0.6), (0.5, 0.2, 0.8), (0.1, 0.2, 0.7), (0.1, 0.3, 0.9), (0.2, 0.4, 0.8)$ denote the edges which are labelled $f(0.3, 0.2, 0.6) = \{a_1, a_2\}, f(0.2, 0.1, 0.6) = \{a_2, a_3\}, f(0.5, 0.2, 0.8) = \{a_3, a_4\}, f(0.1, 0.2, 0.7) = \{a_4, a_5\}, f(0.1, 0.3, 0.9) = \{a_5, a_6\}, f(0.2, 0.4, 0.8) = \{a_6, a_7\},$

Let $\mathcal{H} = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7, (0.3, 0.2, 0.6), (0.2, 0.1, 0.6), (0.5, 0.2, 0.8), (0.1, 0.2, 0.7), (0.1, 0.3, 0.9), (0.2, 0.4, 0.8)\}$ be a topological space defined by the topology

$$\tau = \left\{ \mathcal{H}, \emptyset, \{a_1\}, \{a_2, a_3\}, \{a_4\}, \{a_5, a_6\}, \{a_7\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3\}, \{a_1, a_4\}, \{a_1, a_5, a_6\}, \{a_1, a_7\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_4\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_5, a_6\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_7\}, \{a_4, a_5, a_6\}, \{a_4, a_7\}, \{a_5, a_6, a_7\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_5, a_6\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_7\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_5, a_6\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_7\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_5, a_6, a_7\}, \{a_1, a_4, a_5, a_6\}, \{a_1, a_4, a_7\}, \{a_1, a_4, a_7\}, \{a_1, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_7\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_4, a_7\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_5, a_6, a_7\}, \{a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_5, a_6, a_7\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_4, a_7\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6\}, \{a_1, a_5, a_6, a_7\}, \{a_1, a_4, a_7\}, \{a_1, a_4, a_5, a_6\}, \{a_1, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_4, a_5, a_6, a_7\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_6, a_7\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_7\}, \right\}$$

Here for every $\{h\} \in \mathcal{H}$ is open or closed and $|\partial(h)| \leq 2$. By the definition of 3.1, it is a N-Top graph.

Then $\mathcal{S} = \{a_2, a_5, a_7\}$ is a N-Top dom set in V whose maximum and minimum degrees of $\mathcal{T}, \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{F}$ respectively.

	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5	a_6	a_7		a_1a_2	a_2a_3	a_3a_4	a_4a_5	a_5a_6	a_6a_7
\mathcal{T}_P	0.6	0.4	0.5	0.9	0.3	0.1	0.3	$\mathcal{T}_Q(\max)$	0.6	0.5	0.9	0.9	0.3	0.3
\mathcal{I}_P	0.7	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.5	$\mathcal{I}_Q(\max)$	0.7	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.6	0.6
\mathcal{F}_P	0.3	0.6	0.1	0.6	0.5	0.8	0.6	$\mathcal{F}_Q(\min)$	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.5	0.5	0.6

	a_1a_2	a_2a_3	a_3a_4	a_4a_5	a_5a_6	a_6a_7
$\mathcal{T}_Q(\min)$	0.4	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.1
$\mathcal{I}_Q(\min)$	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.5
$\mathcal{F}_Q(\max)$	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.6	0.8	0.9

Therefore N-top dom set is $\mathcal{S} = \{a_2, a_5, a_7\}$.

$$\tau_\gamma(P_7) = \lceil 7/3 \rceil = \lceil 2.333 \rceil > 2.$$

Lemma .2. Let \mathcal{C}_n be a N-cycle with n -vertices which is a N-Top graph. Then the N-Top dom number $\tau_\gamma(\mathcal{C}_n) \geq \lceil n/3 \rceil$.

Example 3.7.

Let a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5 and a_6 denote the vertices and $(0.1, 0.3, 0.9), (0.2, 0.1, 0.7), (0.5, 0.2, 0.1), (0.4, 0.2, 0.7), (0.5, 0.3, 0.8), (0.3, 0.5, 0.7)$ denote the edges which are labelled $f(0.1, 0.3, 0.9) = \{a_1, a_2\}, f(0.2, 0.1, 0.7) = \{a_2, a_3\}, f(0.5, 0.2, 0.1) = \{a_3, a_4\}, f(0.4, 0.2, 0.7) = \{a_4, a_5\}, f(0.5, 0.3, 0.8) = \{a_5, a_6\}, f(0.3, 0.5, 0.7) = \{a_6, a_1\},$

Let $\mathcal{H} = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6, (0.1, 0.3, 0.9), (0.2, 0.1, 0.7), (0.5, 0.2, 0.1), (0.4, 0.2, 0.7), (0.5, 0.3, 0.8), (0.3, 0.5, 0.7)\}$ be a topological space defined by the topology

$$\tau = \left\{ \mathcal{H}, \emptyset, \{a_1\}, \{a_2\}, \{a_3\}, \{a_4\}, \{a_5\}, \{a_6\}, \{a_1, a_2\}, \{a_1, a_3\}, \{a_1, a_4\}, \{a_1, a_5\}, \{a_1, a_6\}, \{a_2, a_3\}, \{a_2, a_4\}, \{a_2, a_5\}, \{a_2, a_6\}, \{a_3, a_4\}, \{a_3, a_5\}, \{a_3, a_6\}, \{a_4, a_5\}, \{a_4, a_6\}, \{a_5, a_6\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_4\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_5\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_6\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_5\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_6\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_6\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_4\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_5\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_6\}, \{a_3, a_4, a_5\}, \{a_3, a_4, a_6\}, \{a_4, a_5, a_6\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_4, a_6\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6\}, \{a_1, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_4, a_5, a_6\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_5, a_6\}, \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5\}, \{a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6\}, \{a_2, a_4, a_5, a_6\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_4, a_6\}, \{a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5\}, \{a_3, a_5, a_6\} \right\}$$

Here for every $\{h\} \in \mathcal{H}$ is open and $|\partial(h)| \leq 2$. By the definition of 3.1, it is a N-Top graph.

Then $\mathcal{S} = \{a_3, a_6\}$ is a N-Top dom set in V whose maximum and minimum degrees of $\mathcal{T}, \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{F}$ respectively.

	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5	a_6		a_1a_2	a_2a_3	a_3a_4	a_4a_5	a_5a_6	a_6a_1
\mathcal{T}_P	0.3	0.2	0.6	0.9	0.5	0.7	$\mathcal{T}_Q(\max)$	0.3	0.6	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.7
\mathcal{I}_P	0.5	0.8	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.3	$\mathcal{I}_Q(\max)$	0.8	0.8	0.3	0.5	0.4	0.5
\mathcal{F}_P	0.7	0.1	0.7	0.5	0.6	0.1	$\mathcal{F}_Q(\min)$	0.1	0.1	0.5	0.5	0.1	0.1

	a_1a_2	a_2a_3	a_3a_4	a_4a_5	a_5a_6	a_6a_1
$\mathcal{T}_Q(\min)$	0.1	0.2	0.5	0.4	0.5	0.3
$\mathcal{I}_Q(\min)$	0.3	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.5
$\mathcal{F}_Q(\max)$	0.7	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.8	0.7

Therefore N-Top dom set is $\mathcal{S} = \{a_3, a_6\}$.

$$\tau_\gamma(C_6) = \lceil 6/3 \rceil = 2.$$

Lemma .3. Let (\mathcal{K}_n) be a N-complete graph with n -vertices ($n = 2, 3$) which is a N-Top graph. Then the N-Top dom number $\tau_\gamma(\mathcal{K}_n) = 1$.

Example 3.8.

Let a_1, a_2 and a_3 denote the vertices and $(0.1, 0.4, 0.9), (0.05, 0.4, 0.8), (0.1, 0.3, 0.8)$ denote the edges which are labelled $f(0.1, 0.4, 0.9) = \{a_1, a_2\}, f(0.05, 0.4, 0.8) = \{a_2, a_3\}, f(0.1, 0.3, 0.8) = \{a_3, a_1\}$,

Let $\mathcal{H} = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, (0.1, 0.4, 0.9), (0.05, 0.4, 0.8), (0.1, 0.3, 0.8)\}$ be a topological space defined by the topology

$$\tau = \{ \mathcal{H}, \emptyset, \{a_1\}, \{a_2\}, \{a_3\}, \{a_1, a_2\}, \{a_1, a_3\}, \{a_2, a_3\} \}$$

Here for every $\{h\} \in \mathcal{H}$ is open and $|\partial(h)| \leq 2$. By the definition 3.1, it is a N-Top graph.

Then $\mathcal{S} = \{a_1\}$ and $\{a_2, a_3\}$ is a N-Top dom set in V whose maximum and minimum degrees of $\mathcal{T}, \mathcal{I}, \mathcal{F}$ respectively.

	a_1	a_2	a_3
T_A	0.5	0.3	0.1
I_A	0.4	0.6	0.9
F_A	0.7	0.8	0.2

	a_1a_2	a_2a_3	a_3a_1
$\mathcal{T}_P(\max)$	0.5	0.3	0.5
$\mathcal{I}_P(\max)$	0.6	0.9	0.9
$\mathcal{F}_P(\min)$	0.7	0.2	0.2

	a_1a_2	a_2a_3	a_3a_1
$\mathcal{T}_Q(\min)$	0.3	0.1	0.1
$\mathcal{I}_Q(\min)$	0.4	0.6	0.4
$\mathcal{F}_Q(\max)$	0.8	0.8	0.7

Therefore N-Top dom set is $\mathcal{S} = \{a_1\}$, whose top dom number is given by

$$\tau_\gamma(\mathcal{K}_3) = 1.$$

Remark 3.2. The interrelationship among N-Top dom set as given below

4 Conclusion

This paper has focused on calculating the dominating number of N-Top graph G by using top domination conditions. The Top dom condition is introduced in new method to find the domination number. The N-Top domination for some standard N-graphs such as a path, cycle are specified. The future study can be continued by forming different types of N-Top domination set with various applications.

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